

WP 2220 - SI-traceable system development

Report on the laboratory calibration of PFR and PSR

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Introduction

The Precision lunar FilterRadiometer (PFR-98-L-002) and the Precision SpectroRadiometer (PSR#009) have been calibrated in the calibration facilities of PMOD/WRC in yearly intervals since the manufacturing of the instruments. The irradiance standard used at PMOD/WRC are FEL lamps that have an expanded relative uncertainty of the order of 2-3%. Within the framework of the EMPIR 19ENV04 MAPP project, a laser-based calibration, with source uncertainties of less than 0.2 %, was possible for both instruments at the TUNable Lasers In Photometry (TULIP) facility of the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Braunschweig, Germany. The results of these calibrations and comparisons to the PMOD/WRC ones are presented in this report.

Calibration of Lunar-PFR

The PFR-98-L-002 is equipped with four independent narrow spectral channels centred at 412 nm, 500 nm, 675 nm, and 862 nm. The interference filters have a full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) of 4 nm to 5 nm and an optical density of 6 for out-of-band transmittance. The PFR is sealed with dry nitrogen, to prolong the lifetime of the filters and electronics. The four detectors of the PFR are photodiodes with linearity of better than 0.02%. A Peltier-type thermostatic system stabilizes the temperature of the detectors holder to 20 ± 0.1 °C. The signal of the PFR (in Volts), is acquired by a 22-bit data acquisition system (SACRAM) specifically designed for the PFR. Its precision and linearity have been evaluated against a calibrated voltage source and has been found to be better than 0.01% in the range of -5V to +10V. The field of view (FOV) of the instrument is 2.5° FWHM with a slope angle of 0.7° and a plateau of 1.2°. The has been measured with meridian and almucantar scans of the full Moon in an area of $\pm 3^\circ$ around the Moon and shows a spatial homogeneity of 99.5% over $\pm 0.25^\circ$ from the operational position.

The Lunar-PFR PFR-98-L-002 Lunar was calibrated in November 2021 at PTB following the same procedure as the Sun-PFR , PFR-98-N-001 [1], calibrated in January-February 2021. The spectral irradiance responsivities of all channels of the PFR-98-L-002 radiometer were determined both for the in-band and out-of-band spectral ranges. For the measurements, the radiometer was installed on the detector stage of the TULIP setup (Figure 1) and aligned so that the protective window of the radiometer was perpendicular to the optical axis. The position of the radiometric apertures of the filter radiometer channels is well known from the design drawings of the instruments. Additionally, the aperture positions

on the optical axis were verified by performing a set of measurements at different distances from the micro-lens array. For this purpose, the ratio of the signals from the filter radiometer and the reference trap detector with a limiting aperture mounted in front of it was studied at different distances from the microlens array. The ratio of the signals remains constant at difference distances only if the detectors are measured at the respective positions of their effective radiometric apertures. This was the case for both PFR radiometers.

Figure 1 : PFR installed on the detector stage of the TULIP setup.

The normalized spectral responsivities are shown in Figure 2. The results show that the out-of-band blocking of the filters built in the PFR channels in certain spectral regions are at the level of $1E-3$ or $1E-4$.

Figure 2: Normalized responsivities of the PFR-98-L-002.

Figure 3: Spectral irradiance responsivities and uncertainty budget of the PFR-98-L-002 channels.

The uncertainty (U_s) of the spectral responsivity has been determined using a Monte Carlo simulation algorithm accounting for uncertainty sources related to the spectral power responsivity of the trap detector, current measurements, aperture area, the temporal stability and the homogeneity of the laser irradiance field, of the field of view of the PFR and of the trap detector, the laser wavelength, the positioning of the detectors, and the electronic noise of the PFR signal. The spectral contribution of each component is shown in Figure 3 alongside with the spectral responsivity.

Figure 4: Lamp-Based calibration set up at PMOD/WRC (left) and PTB (right).

The PFR gains are essential to be determined since the laboratory measurements are performed with the lowest gain while for the Moon the highest gain is used. It was determined with an uncertainty of 0.3% at TULIP setup, taking advantage of the spectral responsivity of the instrument and selecting appropriate wavelengths for the stepwise linking of the gain values.

The integral values (s_i) of the spectral irradiance responsivities, $s(\lambda)$, determined at the TULIP were compared with ones based on an irradiance transfer standard (200W HLX-type lamp). The differences between the s_i from the TULIP- and the lamp-based calibrations, Δs_i , are less than 0.3% for all channels (Table 1). Moreover, the lamp-based calibrations performed at PMOD/WRC in regular intervals since 2015 were analyzed using the TULIP-obtained information, showing scattered differences within $\pm 1\%$ ($k=2$) (Figure 5), verifying the stability of the instrument in this period.

Figure 5: Comparison of lamp-based calibration of PFR-98-L-002 at PMOD/WRC since 2015 to the low uncertainty TULIP calibration.

Table 1: Calibration results of PFR-98-L-002 at the TULIP setup: centroid wavelength λ , spectral responsivity (s) at minimum gain, combined expanded relative uncertainty (U_s) and differences Δs .

λ (nm)	861.75	675.39	501.39	411.95
s ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}\text{m}^2$)	12.96	6.80	9.78	10.88
U_s (% , $k=2$)	0.26	0.18	0.25	0.27
Δs (%)	-0.10	0.20	0.20	0.30

The Lunar-PFR has been characterized at the state-of-the-art facilities of PTB achieving an uncertainty of less than 0.4 % ($k=2$) in the calibration. Equivalent calibration results between laser- and lamp-based calibrations of the PFR has been retrieved at PTB, giving confidence of the stability of the instrument within 1% for the homogeneous re-evaluation of the lamp-based calibration performed at PMOD/WRC since 2015.

Calibration of PSR

The Precision Solar Spectroradiometer (PSR) is a grating-type array spectroradiometer, developed as a reference instrument for spectral solar irradiance measurements in the spectral range from 300 nm to 1040 nm and for the determination of aerosol optical depth . The uncertainty budget of the spectral responsivity of the PSR instruments [2] showed that a significant uncertainty source is the uncertainty of the irradiance standard used in the calibration. The PSR was transferred to PTB for a TULIP-based calibration. Since the instrument is sensitive to movement all the characterization, stray light correction [3], wavelength calibration and lamp-based calibration, were also repeated at PTB.

The PSR#009 was measured at PTB to determine their spectral irradiance responsivities. In order to calibrate the spectroradiometer, the wavelength scale, and the straylight correction matrix were determined to access the associated measurement uncertainties. The effect of the ambient temperature was not especially investigated, as the detector is temperature controlled. The linearity of the PSR detector and electronics have been accessed in previous work at PMOD/WRC and PTB and it is better than 99.5%.

Figure 6 : PSR on the TULIP setup

A comparison of the straylight correction matrices for PSR#009 is given below. Figure 5 shows the straylight correction matrix measured at PTB with the EKSPILA setup, while Figure 6 shows the matrix measured at PMOD/WRC before the visit to PTB. There are small changes in the wavelength scale, that also affect the shape and intensity of the second and third order dispersion features.

Figure 7: Straylight correction matrix measured at PTB in Nov.2021 (left) and at PMOD in Dec.2019 (right)

The calibration of the spectral irradiance responsivity was done with a calibrated 250 W HLX-type working standard lamp at PTB, using a combination of 2 distances (870 mm and 718 mm) to minimize the noise

levels and the uncertainty of the calibration in the UV and NIR region where the emitted irradiance and the responsivity of the PSR are low respectively. The PTB calibration results using the PTB stray light correction, were compared with the ones performed at PMOD/WRC before (10.2021) and after the PTB calibration (08.2022) and after the Izaña campaign (12.2022). In Figure 9 the afore mentioned responsivity functions and their deviations are shown. The agreement is within the uncertainty of the calibration, however an offset of 0.67 % is observed. The origin of the offset seems to come from the distance measurements in the two setups and not from non-linearities, wavelength shifts or any other correction or change of the responsivity of the instrument during transportation. The wavy features in the responsivity deviations originate from the wavelength scale adjustments and the noise reduction procedure through the 2 distances combination and the smoothing splines. The deviation of the wavelength scale of the PSR at the calibration dates, has been accounted in the analysis, is spectral dependent and is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 8 : Lamp based calibrations of PSR_009. Top panel: Response function measured at PTB on 2021.11.05 (black), and at PMOD on 2021.10.31 (blue), 2022.08.23 (green), 2022.12.08 (orange). Lower panel: deviation of the responsivities measured at PMOD to PTB. The grey area indicates the combined expanded uncertainty of the PTB calibration.

Figure 9: Difference in nm between pixel-to-wavelength function measured in 11.2021 (PTB) and, in 08.2022 and in 12.2022 (PMOD) (difference = PMOD-PTB).

The uncertainty budget of the PTB and PMOD/WRC calibrations are shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14. In the UV and NIR region the noise (dark correction) of the measurement is the dominate uncertainty source while in the Vis the uncertainty of the irradiance source. The reference plane definition is also a significant uncertainty source, in the current analysis an uncertainty of 6 mm (1σ) has been considered.

Figure 10 : Uncertainty budget of PSR responsivity based of the calibration at PTB at a distance of 882 mm and 250 W HLX lamp.

Figure 11: Uncertainty budget of PSR responsivity based of the calibration at PMOD at a distance of 2679 mm and 1000 W FEL lamp.

The tunable laser-based calibration of the PSR has been performed at the TULIP setup following the same principle as in the case of the filter radiometers. The aim of this calibration is to try to improve the uncertainty of the responsivity and identify possible bias errors in the lamp-based calibration procedure. The reference plane of the PSR was determined with respect to reference detector, a discrepancy of -6 mm to the initial value was determined and applied to the lamp calibrations analysis as offset and uncertainty.

The whole operational spectral range of the spectrometer (315 nm – 1035 nm) was scanned repeatedly, to access the reproducibly this type of calibration. For the analysis the same procedure and corrections applied in the lamp calibration was followed (dark, non-linearity and stray light correction). The latest stray light correction matrix and the wavelength scale were used. Due to the geometry of the TULIP setup the alignment uncertainty is minimized (her set to zero) since the PSR field of view is overfilled with a homogeneous beam. The noise of the TULIP calibration was calculated based on the contribution of the combined uncertainty noise of dark and signal on the dark corrected signal, to the integral over ± 10 nm from the centroid wavelength (Figure 15 – TULIP: dark correction). Significant improvement has been accomplished by a factor ranging between 5 and 30 depending on the spectral region (Figure 15). Similarly, the combined uncertainty of measurement and smoothing, accounting for uncertainties of dark, non - linearity corrections, alignment and smoothing) is significantly lower.

Figure 12 : Uncertainty contributions in the PSR response of dark correction and measurements and smoothing (dark, non - linearity corrections, alignment and smoothing) for the TULIP and lamp (FEL) based calibrations.

The effect on the selected spectral interval for the integration of the line-spread-functions (LSF) measured at TULIP has been investigated by selecting different wavelength offsets from the peak wavelength ranging from ± 5 nm to ± 20 nm and compared to the integral over ± 10 nm (Figure 15). No strong dependency was observed, with differences to be within $\pm 0.05\%$ ($k=2$) uncertainty that has been included in the final uncertainty budget of the TULIP based calibration.

Finally the wavelength-pixel scale from the pulsed laser systems has been compared to the TULIP one (Figure 16). An offset of 0.25 nm has been found and an increase of the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the LSF due to different geometry to the incident light. Above 950 nm the resolution of the laser beam is increased therefore the observed differences are disregarded (Figure 16, lower panel).

Figure 13: The effect on the selected spectral interval for the integration of the LSF measured at TULIP. Different integration regions relative to the peak wavelength ranging from ± 5 nm to ± 20 nm are compared to the integral over ± 10 nm.

Figure 14: Wavelength scale residuals of the dispersion function retrieved based on measurements at the TULIP setup (red) and difference to the initial dispersion function (upper panel). FWHM of the simulated LSF by a Gaussian function (red: TULIP, blue: pulsed laser system) (lower panel).

All lamp-based calibrations have been brought to the TULIP based wavelengths scale and compared. The spectral responsivity functions are presented in Figure 17 upper panel. The errorbars on the TULIP-based calibration show the combined expanded uncertainty based on

In lower panel of Figure 17 the differences between the TULIP-based calibration and the lamp-based ones are compared. The offsets derived as the median difference over the spectral range 550 nm to 800 nm has been subtracted. A difference 0.3% in the calculated offset between the lamp calibrations at PTB and PMOD/WRC seem to be arising from the entrance plane definition. The remaining offset, 0.37%, resembles the results of TULIP- QASUME calibration, and it is under investigation.

The underestimation of the responsivity in the range 315 nm to 450 nm from the lamp calibration method is consistent with the comparison of AOD to the PFR and ToA solar spectrum [4] compared to the TSIS-1 HSRS [5].

Further analysis will be performed to minimize uncertainties from the LSF interpolation and stray light correction and access the remaining discrepancies.

Figure 15: Response deviation between TULIP and Lamp-based calibrations (%). The deviations have been adjusted for the median offset in the region 550 nm to 800 nm.

References

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